

D5.1

Assessment along the IWW corridor and a surrounding disaster affected area, using multi-source remote sensing data

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
ASPP	Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling
BSI	Bare Soil Index
CHM	Canopy Height Model
CRP	Calibrated Reflectance Panel
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DEM	Digital Elevation Models
DLL	Dynamic-link library
EO cameras	Electro-Optical Cameras
FCN network	Fully Convolutional Network
GCP	Ground Control Point
GCS	Ground Control Station
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system
IBM	Image Based Modelling
IMS/COP	Information Management System/ Common Operating Picture
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
OSM	OpenStreetMap
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
IoT	Internet of things
IoU	Intersection over Union
IR cameras	Infrared Cameras
IWW	Inland Water Ways
JDL/DFIG	Joint Directors of Laboratories/ Data Fusion Information Group
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSWI	Land Surface Water Index
LULC	Land Cover Land Use
ML	Machine Learning
MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
MSI	Multispectral Instrument
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit

Abbreviation	Meaning
ResNet network	Residual network
RMS	Root Mean Square
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RS-MMS	RS-based multiscale monitoring system
RTSP	Real-Time Streaming Protocol
SAM	Segment Anything Model
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SBAS	Satellite-based augmentation systems
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SWIR	Short Wavelength InfraRed
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UI	User Interface
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service

Executive Summary

The deliverable 5.1 focuses on the description of methods and tools that have been developed for the assessment along the Inland Waterway (IWW) corridors and the surrounding disaster areas that could be affected by floods, land deformations, etc. using multi source remote sensing data in the framework of the PLOTTO project. The developed methods were applied on Use Cases B (Budapest region) and C (Wallonia region) and their products serve as reference data for post disaster damage assessment and routine monitoring procedures.

In chapter 1, the comprehensive framework for monitoring inland waterways is described, ensuring regular maintenance and early hazard detection. The framework employs advanced computer vision and machine learning techniques for effective monitoring and damage management, while it integrates various data from satellites, UAVs and ground-based sensors. In addition, the data acquisition methods and data processing workflow are thoroughly described for each Use Case to produce Digital Elevation Models, 3D representations including both point clouds and 3D meshes, as well as orthomosaics. The acquired data, including RGB, multispectral data, and point clouds, serve as the basis for deformation and other types of alterations detection and will be used as reference data for creating 4D representations of important infrastructures over different time instances.

In chapter 2, the methodology that was developed on water mapping is presented. For effective river monitoring and assessment of the affected areas during and after events, aiding management, and response efforts, the optical sensing instruments on satellites, such as the Sentinel-2 constellation, were leveraged. In this section, the state-of-the-art deep learning algorithms for inland water mapping were used to create binary water maps, improving upon traditional indices like Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI). These water maps serve as foundational products for subsequent methods and applications focusing on flood and island detection, and river width estimation.

In chapter 3, the methods for the multi-sensor synoptic assessment for different disaster scenarios are presented. First, by defining the various disaster scenarios for each Use Case and the sensor strategy that needs to be followed. The damage assessment tool that was developed focuses on the definition of abnormal water coverage and detection of the affected infrastructure utilizing all the available data that were acquired and integrated on the Ground Control Station.

The deliverable is intended for public use, and it will particularly be helpful for the partners involved in the design of the PLOTTO platform.

1 Conceptual Framework for routine open IWW corridor monitoring

1.1 Scope and Objective

In the context of the PLOTO project, a comprehensive framework for monitoring Inland Waterway (IWW) corridors has been designed and implemented. This framework ensures regular and efficient maintenance and facilitates the early detection of damage, degradation, and emerging hazards, enabling the rapid inspection and assessment of damage and IWW performance during and after hazardous events.

The framework integrates data from three remote sensing levels: satellites, UAVs, and ground-based sensors. The focus is on the optimal use of various sensor types, both active and passive, to address the specific monitoring needs of individual IWW elements and different hazard scenarios in a holistic manner. It equally addresses the need for regular monitoring, degradation detection, and the management of developing hazard situations, as well as post-event damage scenarios. To satisfy the diverse information requirement, state-of-the-art computer vision and machine learning techniques have been used by the framework.

Details about the conceptual framework that has been designed and developed within the WP5 and its internal components and techniques are presented in the continuation.

1.2 The components of the Remote Sensing-based Multiscale Monitoring System

PLOTO, through its provisions for remote sensing-based monitoring capacity combines satellite-based data with information collected through UAVs, to provide a holistic approach. In this context the use of UAVs enables the creation of imagery or laser scanning, generating detailed geometric and semantic information on the aforementioned objects. Additionally, it allows for the generation of large-area surface and height models, as well as ortho maps, which will serve as backdrops for decision-making and form the basis for integrating hazard scenarios. On the other hand, satellite-based data could be used to carry out fast and synoptic wide-area assessments and identify extensive damage, flooding, landslide blockage etc.

Provided the above, the key role of the conceptual framework for routine open IWW corridor monitoring that has been designed by PLOTO refers to a “Remote Sensing-based Multiscale Monitoring System”. This system encompasses a set of data-acquisition components (UAV / Satellite) and analysis techniques and methodologies that exports results related to the main objectives of the project. An overview of the RS-based multiscale monitoring system of the IWW corridors and wider areas (including its functional components) is presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

As far as the data acquisition process is concerned, a unified Ground Control Station (GCS) has been designed and implemented. The role of the GCS is twofold: a) to support the management of the UAV missions and the related measurements and b) to support the use of satellite data by project components through requesting, gathering and providing data gathered from satellite data providers, while being available and related to the methodologies /analysis techniques operated within the project. In this respect, the GCS is responsible for (among others) the UAVs’ flight planning as well as for the management of the data that will be gathered by these platforms and sensors to make these

data available to the rest of the project's components. Additionally, satellite remote sensing data will be selected enabling the activation of the wider areas monitoring levels. Remote sensing data and Copernicus products will be collected by the GCS, making these available for further processing and analysis by the remaining project's components. Advanced methodologies for a) 3D analysis using photogrammetric means and ML, mainly focusing on deep learning methodologies and tensor Algebra decomposition, b) ground deformation assessment using SBAS approach, c) change detection using deep learning methodologies, and d) flood extent delineation based on Bayesian approach will be employed for generating the RS-MMS products.

Figure 1: Main components of the operational IWW corridor monitoring procedure and the link between them.

Figure 2: The RS-based multiscale monitoring system.

1.3 PLOTO GCS and the data acquisition/selection component

The GCS facilitates the data acquisition process both for the in-situ and remote data acquisition in the context of each pilot. Data that are related to each pilot area and each pilot scenario will be gathered either using UAV drones or through satellite data providers and will be forwarded to corresponding components for further analysis and processing. In this context, the GCS system has been designed to be agnostic to specific drone characteristics and payload types. Figure 3 below depicts the GCS high-level architecture.

Figure 3: GCS high-level architecture.

Considering the high-level visualization of the architecture above, it becomes apparent that the module in consideration is composed of the following set of components:

- the **“Satellite Data Request Configurator”**, which configures the satellite data request parameters according to the requirements of each pilot scenario.
- the **“Satellite Data Manager”**, which supports the communication with the satellite data providers, requesting the required data, receiving and storing these in the project’s data repository (PLOT0 middleware).
- the **“Drone Missions & Data Acquisition”**, which supports drone flight and mission planning, monitoring and data acquisition and storing to the project’s data repository (PLOT0 middleware). The management and monitoring functionalities that are supported are provided through a graphical User Interface (UI) that is integrated with the PLOT0 IMS/COP system.

More details on the GCS-provided functionalities and its components are presented in Section 1.5.

1.4 Satellite and drone monitoring capability

The integration of satellite and drone monitoring capabilities offers a sophisticated approach to the situational awareness of inland waterways. This combined methodology leverages the unique characteristics of both technologies to provide a more efficient and accurate understanding of these considered operational environments. The capabilities/characteristics of satellite and drone

technologies and how these are utilized to implement accurate and efficient data fetch inside the PLOTO platform, also highlighting how their integration enhances our ability to monitor and assess inland waterways.

1.5 Enhanced Drone and Satellite Ground Control Station (GCS)

The component that provides the PLOTO project with satellite and drone monitoring capabilities is the GCS. Its main objective is to provide the rest of the PLOTO components' environmental data that are required for analysis purposes. These data could be acquired either by the satellite providers or through drones that could fly around the area by users with related access rights.

The GCS component has been designed to be agnostic to the data providers and the data types that could be managed. As a result, it is not agnostic to the Satellite data provider and the type of drones that could be used, as well as the type and format of data that could be acquired and managed.

Figure 3 depicts the GCS high-level architecture. The system is meticulously structured to ensure efficient data collection, processing, and dissemination through its various components. As mentioned above, it is composed of the following three sub-components:

- the **“Satellite Data Request Configurator”**: This component plays a pivotal role in tailoring data acquisition to meet specific monitoring scenarios and data requirements. Users can define various scenarios and data needs, which the configurator translates into specific requests to the Satellite Data Manager. This ensures that only relevant and required data is collected, optimizing resource utilization and data processing efficiency.
- the **“Satellite Data Manager”**: This module receives and processes data from satellites. It acts as the primary interface between the satellite data and the rest of the system. The manager is responsible for data validation, preprocessing, and ensuring the integrity and accuracy of the data before it is used or stored. It is executed periodically (according to each scenario's needs) requesting and acquiring different versions of the satellite data per time.
- the **“Drone Missions & Data Acquisition”**: This module is tasked with planning, executing, and managing drone missions. It interfaces with each drone's Control Station to direct drone operations and collects data from the drones. Additionally, it integrates with the PLOTO IMS/COP system to support comprehensive mission planning and operational control, ensuring that drone missions align with the overall data acquisition strategy.

The GCS component supports the management of data gathered by the following two data source types:

- **Satellite Data**: This source represents comprehensive data collected by orbiting satellites. The satellites continuously monitor and gather various types of data, which are then transmitted to the Satellite Data Manager within the GCS. This data can include imagery, environmental parameters, and other relevant metrics.
- **Drone Data**: Drones, equipped with sensors and cameras, collect data from specific areas of interest. Each drone comes with its own Drone Control Station, which is responsible for the operational control of the drone. This station ensures that the drone is correctly positioned and managed to gather the necessary data. The collected data is then relayed to the Drone Missions & Data Acquisition module.

The GCS component has been integrated with other PLOTO components, such as the PLOTO IMS/COP system and the PLOTO Middleware.

- **PLOTO IMS/COP** plays a significant role in enhancing mission management and operational control, providing a comprehensive interface for mission planning and real-time adjustments.
- The **PLOTO Middleware** ensures that the data transfer process is secure and efficient, maintaining data integrity and compatibility. It provides a Data Repository that acts as a robust storage solution, supporting scalable and secure data storage. It allows for easy access and retrieval of data, facilitating analysis and decision-making processes, making all gathered data easily available to the rest of the PLOTO components for further processing, analysis and visualization purposes.

1.6 Multi-Satellite Ground Station

The number of satellite data providers has been growing rapidly in recent years due to advancements in technology and an increasing demand for satellite imagery and related services. Currently, several satellite data providers are available worldwide, offering a wide range of services in the domain of earth observation and geospatial analytics. Typically, these satellite data providers are provided their data (images, sensor measurements etc.) through an interface API/web service, enabling third-party services to use this interface, request specific data and download these. The usage of this interface could be either free or restricted to public access.

In the case of the PLOTO project, the use of Sentinel satellites and data that are provided by these types of satellites has been selected. Additional options for satellite data providers (such as SPOT6/7) have been considered and analysed. However, the requirement for data introduced by the end-users and the processing/analysis techniques owners (mainly WP5 partners), guided us in the selection of the Sentinel satellites as the main satellite data provider that would be used by the GCS component.

1.6.1 Sentinel Missions

The European Space Agency (ESA) has developed a family of missions called Sentinels specifically for the operational needs of Copernicus. Each Sentinel mission is based on a constellation of satellites to fulfil revisit and coverage requirements, providing robust datasets for Copernicus services. These satellites are designed to monitor various environmental and climatic conditions on the Earth's surface, atmosphere, and oceans. The data collected by Sentinel satellites is used in a wide array of applications, including agriculture, forestry, land use, water management, and disaster response. Some of the Sentinel Missions are still in the preparation stage and have pending launches. Samples of the satellite data are presented in continuation (Figures 4 & 5).

Figure 4: Sample of Sentinel 2A Band 6 in Romania.

Figure 5: Sample of Sentinel 2A Band 3 in Romania.

Figure 5 depicts a satellite overlay map, where satellite imagery is superimposed on a geographic map. The satellite image appears in grayscale, providing detailed views of terrain, land use, and water bodies, whereas the underlying map shows the geographical context, including cities, roads, and natural landmarks.

Several types of data are provided by Sentinel satellites. Table 1 provides an overview of these types of data:

Sentinel Satellite Mission	Data characteristics
Sentinel-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). • Capabilities: All-weather, day-and-night imaging for land and ocean services. • Applications: Monitoring sea ice, forest mapping, surface deformation, and emergency response.
Sentinel-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Multi-spectral optical imagery. • Capabilities: High-resolution optical imaging with 13 spectral bands. • Applications: Land cover classification, vegetation health monitoring, water quality assessment, and disaster management.
Sentinel-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Ocean and land monitoring. • Capabilities: Instruments for sea surface topography, sea and land surface temperature, and ocean and land colour. • Applications: Marine and land ecosystem monitoring, climate research, and weather forecasting.
Sentinel-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Atmospheric composition monitoring. • Capabilities: High-resolution monitoring of trace gases and aerosols in the atmosphere. • Applications: Air quality monitoring, climate research, and UV radiation measurement.
Sentinel-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Atmospheric composition monitoring. • Capabilities: Monitoring of trace gases such as ozone, methane, and carbon monoxide. • Applications: Air quality monitoring, climate research, and health assessments.
Sentinel-6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Radar altimetry for sea level measurement. • Capabilities: High-precision measurement of sea surface height, wave height, and wind speed. • Applications: Climate monitoring, oceanography, and weather forecasting.
Sentinel-5P	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type: Atmospheric monitoring. • Capabilities: Monitoring of air quality, ozone, and trace gases. • Applications: Air pollution monitoring, climate research, and health assessments.

Table 1: Sentinel missions - data characteristics

In the context of the PLOTO project, taking into consideration the requirements, data provided by the Sentinel-1 & Sentinel-2 have been selected to be used.

1.6.1.1 Sentinel Hub API

The data acquisition from Sentinel 1 & 2 satellites is enabled through the Sentinel HUB API¹. Sentinel Hub is a powerful cloud-based platform designed to facilitate easy access to and processing of satellite imagery from the Copernicus Sentinel satellites and other sources. It is widely used by scientists, researchers, developers, and businesses to monitor environmental changes, conduct land-use analysis, and implement various geospatial applications.

The Sentinel Hub API allows users to programmatically access and download satellite images and data. It provides a suite of tools and endpoints that enable seamless integration with various applications, making satellite data retrieval and processing efficient and customizable. By leveraging the API, GCS can automate the process of fetching satellite imagery, apply custom processing workflows, and provide the satellite data to other PLOT components for further analysis and processing purposes.

Sentinel Hub offers a range of services and features designed to make satellite imagery accessible and usable:

1. Data Integration:

- Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, and Sentinel-5P: Full integration with the Sentinel constellation, providing access to various types of data, such as SAR, multispectral optical imagery, ocean and land monitoring, and atmospheric composition.
- Additional Sources: Support for other satellite data sources such as Landsat, MODIS, and commercial providers.

2. Cloud-Based Processing:

- On-the-Fly Processing: Real-time image processing capabilities, including atmospheric correction, cloud masking, and vegetation indices computation.
- Custom Scripts: Users can create and run custom processing scripts to tailor the data according to specific needs.

3. Visualization and Analysis:

- EO Browser: A web application that allows users to visualize satellite imagery and perform basic analysis without coding.
- Time-Lapse Creation: Tools to create time-lapse videos to visualize changes over time.

4. APIs and Integration:

- Sentinel Hub API: A comprehensive RESTful API that provides endpoints for searching, retrieving, and processing satellite data.
- OGC Services: Support for OGC standards, such as WMS, WMTS, WCS, and WFS for easy integration with GIS applications.

The Sentinel Hub API is designed to be flexible and powerful, allowing users to specify various parameters to customize their data requests. Table 2 shows the main parameters needed for downloading images:

Sensors	Specifications
Instance ID	A unique identifier for your Sentinel Hub account and configuration. It is required for authenticating API requests and accessing specific configurations.
Layer	Specifies the type of data layer you want to download. Examples include true color, false color, NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), and custom layers defined in your configuration.

¹ <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/develop/api/>

Sensors	Specifications
Bounding Box (BBOX)	Defines the geographic area of interest. It is provided as an array of four coordinates representing the minimum and maximum longitude and latitude [minLon, minLat, maxLon, maxLat].
Time Interval	The time period for which you want to retrieve data. This is specified with a start and end date in the format YYYY-MM-DD.
Resolution	Specifies the spatial resolution of the imagery in meters per pixel. Higher resolutions provide more detail but result in larger file sizes.
Format	The output format of the downloaded image. Common formats include JPEG, PNG, and GeoTIFF.
CRS (Coordinate Reference System)	Specifies the coordinate reference system in which the data should be delivered. Common options include EPSG:4326 (WGS 84), EPSG:3857 (Web Mercator), among others.
Cloud Coverage	An optional parameter to filter images based on the percentage of cloud cover. This helps in obtaining clearer images for analysis.
Preview Mode	An optional parameter that, when enabled, generates quick previews of the requested area, typically in lower resolution, useful for preliminary checks before downloading high-resolution data.
Processing Parameters	Additional parameters for custom image processing. This can include atmospheric correction settings, computation of spectral indices (e.g., NDVI, EVI), mosaicking options, and other image enhancement techniques.

Table 2: Sentinel Hub API - parameters

According to the GCS internal design, the satellite data acquisition functionality is supported by two components. The **“Satellite Data Request Configurator”** is the component that prepares the list of parameters that should be requested to the Sentinel HUB API in order to receive the data that are required for each of the pilot scenarios that are executed. This list of parameters is used by the **“Satellite Data Manager”** in order to periodically request and gather the related data. These data are stored in the data repository that is provided by the PLOTTO middleware, in order to be available to the rest PLOTTO components.

1.6.1.2 Pilot sites

The multi-satellite GS leverages satellite images retrieved from the Sentinel satellites to ensure consistency and accuracy in data analysis and application development. Requestors are free to select the area and gather (through the API) the data according to this area. However, for consistency purposes, the layout of the tiles that are used by the Sentinel Hub Browser has been required. Thus, the PLOTTO analysis components could use data produced either from the Sentinel Hub Browser or the Sentinel Hub API. To maintain this tile layout, specific polygons have been defined that match the exact specifications of the images provided by the Sentinel Hub Browser. These polygons delineate the geographical areas of interest, ensuring that the data we fetch corresponds precisely to the areas our models were trained on. A sample of such polygons is presented in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Polygons created to match the pilot area and the Sentinel polygons.

By defining these precise polygons, seamless integration of new data with our existing models without introducing discrepancies, was achieved. This process involves detailed mapping and verification to ensure that each polygon accurately represents the area covered by the original training images. The result is a cohesive and reliable dataset that enhances the performance and accuracy of our project components, allowing for robust data analysis and insightful applications. This meticulous approach guarantees that the imagery retrieved through the Sentinel Hub API perfectly aligns with our established data parameters, fostering consistency across all stages of our project.

Figure 7: Map overlaid with Sentinel Standard Polygon (black grid) and GCS Polygon (red grid).

Figure 7 depicts a geographic map overlaid with two distinct grid systems: the Sentinel Standard Polygon, represented by a black grid, and the GCS Polygon, shown with a red grid. Each rectangle depicted is a pixel of the images produced. The primary objective illustrated is the alignment of the GCS Polygon with the Sentinel Standard Polygon to ensure that the image pixels are correctly mapped and synchronized between the two systems.

The black grid signifies the Sentinel Standard Polygon, the default tiling system used by Sentinel satellites. Each cell within this grid corresponds to a predefined area that the satellite imagery covers, ensuring consistency in how data is captured and referenced across different regions and times.

In contrast, the red grid represents the Ground Control Station (GCS) tiling system. Initially, this grid may not align perfectly with the Sentinel Standard Polygon. Achieving proper alignment is crucial to ensure that the data captured by the GCS matches seamlessly with the satellite data, allowing for accurate analysis and integration.

1.7 Drone Missions & Data Acquisition

With respect to managing drone missions, PLOTO employs the drone ground station as part of the GCS component. This module is specifically designed to fulfil the requirements of PLOTO regarding the creation/planning of drone missions, assignment of these missions to drones, and subsequently uploading the collected data to the PLOTO Middleware (once the mission has been completed). This offered functionality ensures that the data is readily available for all other PLOTO components (upon

request). The management of drone missions is ensured through a robust tool designed to streamline the process of planning, executing, and managing drone missions effectively.

The main list of functionalities that are supported by the Drone Missions & Data Acquisition module is provided to the users through a graphical user interface (UI) (see Figure 8). It is integrated with the PLOTO IMS/COP system that is provided by Satways Ltd. and is based on a legacy IMS/COP system, the ENGAGE IMS/COP that has been enhanced and adapted to the requirements and objectives of the PLOTO project.

Figure 8: UAS Mission Management Perspective.

Tailored specifically for the needs of the PLOTO project, this functionality offers the capacity to users towards creating mission plans in a friendly manner. Users begin by crafting missions through a user-friendly interface (Figure 9) where they can input a mission title, select the UAV best suited for the task from a predefined list, and meticulously define the route that the UAV will follow during its flight.

Figure 9: UAV Mission Create/Update Dialog.

The whole process from creating a mission to collecting the data recorded by the UAV and storing them in PLOTTO Middleware is presented in the following diagram (Figure 10).

Figure 10: UAV mission data acquisition process.

The diagram illustrates the workflow for UAV mission creation, execution, data retrieval, and sharing using the PLOTTO Ground Control Station (GCS). The process is divided into five stages, as follows:

1. Mission Creation in PLOTTO GCS:

- **Define mission title:** The initial step involves specifying a title for the mission.
- **Select drone:** The next step is to select the specific drone to be used for the mission.
- **Define Mission Polygon:** After defining the drone, the mission area or polygon/polyline is defined.
- **Save Mission:** The final step in this stage is saving the mission configuration.

2. Flight Preparation:

- **Select Mission:** The mission is selected from a list of saved missions
- **Export Mission route as .kml:** The mission route is exported in a KML (Keyhole Markup Language) file format.
- **Upload mission .kml in drone:** The exported KML file is then uploaded to the drone.

3. Flight Execution:

- **Launch UAV: The drone is launched.**
- **Fly & Collect data:** The drone flies along the defined mission route and collects data.
- **Land UAV:** After data collection, the drone is landed.

4. Retrieve Collected Data:

- **Select Mission:** The specific mission for which data needs to be retrieved is selected.

- **Upload collected data:** The collected data is uploaded from the drone.

5. Data Sharing:

- **Serve Data through Kafka/Geoserver/Rest API:** The uploaded data is then served through various channels such as Kafka, Geoserver, or REST API for further use and analysis.

This structured workflow ensures a systematic approach to planning, executing, and utilizing UAV missions for data collection and sharing.

One of the standout features of this component is its capability to provide real-time situational awareness through live footage streaming. Users can integrate RTSP (Real-Time Streaming Protocol) URLs to view live video feeds directly within the application interface. This feature not only enhances operational monitoring but also enables operators to make informed decisions in real time, ensuring mission success and safety.

Once a mission is completed, the component facilitates the seamless transfer of recorded data back to the PLOTTO platform. Operators can easily upload and archive valuable mission data, including imagery, sensor readings, and other relevant information. This ensures that all collected data is promptly accessible to other PLOTTO components for further analysis, processing, and decision-making.

Furthermore, the UAV mission management functionality prioritizes user experience and efficiency. It integrates intuitive controls and navigational aids to assist operators in managing complex missions effortlessly. Detailed logging and reporting functionalities capture mission details comprehensively, providing valuable insights for post-mission analysis and optimization.

In summary, the UAV GCS component represents a pivotal asset within the PLOTTO project, combining advanced mission planning capabilities with real-time monitoring and robust data management features. It not only enhances operational efficiency but also ensures compliance with project requirements, fostering a seamless workflow from mission inception to data utilization. This comprehensive toolset is aimed at facilitating drone mission management, empowering users to achieve their objectives with high efficiency and precision.

1.7.1 UAS Mission Management

The functionality of the Unmanned Aerial System (UAS) mission management is supported by the UI that is depicted on Figure 8. It has been designed to streamline the planning, execution, and monitoring of UAS missions. This UI is structured around four main views:

1. UAS Missions View
2. UAS Mission Data View
3. UAS Video Camera View
4. Map View

Each one of these views offers a unique set of functionalities that contribute to a comprehensive mission management experience.

1.7.2 The UAS Missions View

The "UAS Missions" view serves as the command centre for overseeing all UAS missions. It typically features a detailed list showcasing active, completed, and planned missions along with key attributes such as mission name, status, scheduled time, and assigned UAS. Users can interact with this list to access mission details, edit mission parameters, or initiate new missions. This centralized view ensures

that mission planners and operators have a clear and organized overview of all ongoing activities, enabling efficient coordination and management. The ability to track the status and progress of each mission in real time helps in quick decision-making and resource allocation.

In the Figure 11, the UAS Missions view is presented. It includes:

- 1. a set of buttons for creating new mission, deleting the selected mission and filtering, and
- 2. the list of the already created missions, color-coded according to their current status.

Figure 11: The UAS Mission view.

1.7.3 The UAS Mission Data View

In the "UAS Mission Data" view, users can delve into the granular details of each mission's performance and outcomes. This view aggregates telemetry data, sensor readings, environmental metrics, and other critical information collected during the mission.

Figure 12: The UAS Mission Data view.

The UAS Mission Data view is presented in Figure 12. This view includes the following:

1. Mission Status Label, which shows the selected mission status (Waiting Dispatch, Send, Completed) and is color-coded.
2. Show route on map button, which shows/hides the route defined on the map.
3. Export route to .kml file.
4. List/Grid of data recorded during the mission, where all the data uploaded and linked to the selected mission can be found.
5. Edit mission button, which is used to edit all mission information, and upload new data.

1.7.4 The UAS Video Camera View

The "UAS Mission Video Camera" view provides a real-time visual feed from the UAS's onboard cameras. This video stream is crucial for missions that require visual confirmation and monitoring, such as surveillance, reconnaissance and environmental assessment. Operators can watch live footage to track the UAS's progress, verify mission objectives, and respond promptly to any unexpected situations. Additionally, the ability to review recorded video post-mission allows for thorough debriefing and analysis, ensuring that every aspect of the mission can be evaluated and learned from. This visual perspective enhances situational awareness and provides a tangible connection to the mission environment.

1.7.5 The Map View

The "Map" view offers a geographical representation of the mission area, enriched with various overlays that display mission paths, waypoints, no-fly zones, and other pertinent geographical information. This spatial visualization is indispensable for navigation and operational planning. It allows users to plan and adjust flight routes, ensure adherence to airspace regulations, and coordinate

movements with ground teams and other aerial units. This geographic context helps in maintaining operational safety, optimizing mission routes, and achieving mission goals with precision.

Together, these four views form a robust and integrated platform for UAS mission management. They provide a seamless flow of information and control, from initial planning and real-time monitoring to post-mission analysis. By offering a blend of strategic oversight, detailed data analytics, real-time visual feedback, and geographic context, the "UAS Mission Management Perspective" ensures that operators can manage their missions with the highest level of efficiency, safety, and effectiveness. This integrated approach not only enhances operational capabilities but also fosters continuous improvement and innovation in UAS mission planning and execution.

1.7.6 Sensor Integration

In the context of advanced monitoring of Inland Waterways with Unmanned Aerial Systems, these systems could integrate various sensor technologies, which is crucial for collecting comprehensive and accurate information about the IWW networks. The deployment of multiple sensors, including Electro-Optical (EO) and Infrared (IR) cameras, multi-spectral cameras, and LiDAR, provides a multi-faceted approach to surveillance, environmental monitoring, and mapping. Each type of sensor contributes unique capabilities, allowing for detailed analysis and effective management of the IWW network. In the continuation the functionalities and applications of these sensors, highlighting their importance in achieving robust and precise monitoring outcomes will be more thoroughly described.

1.7.6.1 EO/IR Cameras

- **Electro-Optical (EO) Cameras:** These cameras can capture high-resolution visible light images, providing detailed visual information about the IWW network and its surroundings. They can be used for general surveillance of the targeted area.
- **Infrared (IR) Cameras:** These cameras detect heat signatures, allowing for the monitoring of thermal properties of objects and environments. They are particularly useful for detecting changes in water temperature, identifying vessels, and assessing the condition of infrastructure.

1.7.6.2 Multi-Spectral Cameras

- **Functionality:** Multi-spectral cameras capture images in multiple wavelengths across the electromagnetic spectrum. This capability is essential for detailed environmental monitoring, such as assessing vegetation health, detecting water pollution, and analyzing soil composition.
- **Applications:** These cameras will be used to monitor the ecological status of the IWW network, detect anomalies, and support environmental research.

1.7.6.3 LiDAR

- **Principle:** LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) sensors use laser pulses to create high-resolution 3D maps of the terrain. This technology is invaluable for creating accurate topographic maps and assessing physical changes in the landscape.
- **Usage in GCS:** LiDAR data could be used for detailed mapping of the IWW network, identifying changes in land and water boundaries, and detecting potential hazards such as obstacles or sediment buildup.

1.8 GCS deployment, data acquisition and processing

1.8.1 Reference System

The first step of the GCS deployment and data acquisition for each Use Case was the determination of the reference coordinate systems that will be used to conduct the necessary measurements in order to georeference the various products. The necessary Ground Control Points (GCPs) that were placed on the ground in each case were measured using a global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receiver, while the ones that were placed on the facades of the infrastructures and the laser scanner targets were measured using an integrated Total Station in order to georeference them with the minimum constraints ensuring the avoidance of deformations of the shape or size of each infrastructure. The equipment used included the following GNSS receiver and integrated Total Station with the necessary accessories:

- GNSS receiver Trimble R10 with positioning performance horizontal $0.25 \text{ m} \pm 1 \text{ ppm RMS}$ and vertical $0.50 \text{ m} \pm 1 \text{ ppm RMS}$.
- Leica Nova MS60 MultiStation with distance accuracy $1\text{mm} \pm 1.5 \text{ ppm}$ (reflectorless $2 \text{ mm} \pm 2 \text{ ppm}$) and angular accuracy $1''$.
- Emlid Reach RS2+ with the following positioning accuracy: (i) RTK horizontal: $7 \text{ mm} + 1 \text{ ppm}$, vertical: $14 \text{ mm} + 1 \text{ ppm}$, (ii) PPK horizontal: $5 \text{ mm} + 0.5 \text{ ppm}$, vertical: $10 \text{ mm} + 1 \text{ ppm}$ and (iii) static horizontal: $4 \text{ mm} + 0.5 \text{ ppm}$, vertical: $8 \text{ mm} + 1 \text{ ppm}$.

Figure 13: Measuring Ground Control Points and Check Points at Use Case B (left) and C (right).

In particular, for Use Case B (Budapest Area) during the first survey in April 2023 a total number of 19 GCPs and 17 check points were measured, while during the second one in December 2023 a total number of 18 GCPs and 33 check points were measured (Figure 13). For the Use Case C (Wallonia area), a total number of 5 GCPs were measured using just the GNSS receiver. Finally, for Use Case A (Braila

and Galati Port Areas), a total number of 24 GCPs were measured in October 2024 using the GNSS receiver evenly distributed and more than 4 at each site to assess the accuracy.

1.8.2 UAS

The main component of the transportable GCS is the UAS which will provide the data mainly used for the initial 3D modelling, representation and maps of the Use Cases, as well as the routine and post-disaster monitoring. The system includes multi-rotor and/or fixed wing vehicles, depending on special local conditions and the UAS is combined with airborne multispectral, hyperspectral, LIDAR and thermal sensors according to the needs.

The UAS consists of:

- A rigid but lightweight frame,
- A recovery system,
- A flight controller,
- An Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU),
- A power source,
- A launching system,
- Sensors & Payloads,
- A ground communication, command and control station.

During the data acquisition process in both Use Cases B and C the DJI Matrice 300 RTK was used with the DJI Smart Controller Enterprise. In addition, the available sensors and payloads that were used for the data acquisition were the following:

- RGB Camera: DJI Zenmuse P1.
- Multispectral Camera: MicaSense RedEdge-P (with luminosity sensor).
- LiDAR sensor: DJI Zenmuse L1.

Figure 14: The DJI Matrice 300 RTK (left) and the DJI Smart Controller Enterprise (right) that were used for the data acquisition.

In Use Case A, the DJI M3 RTK was used to acquire the digital RGB images, while for the LiDAR data, the DJI Matrice 300 RTK was used with the GEOSUN GS-130X LiDAR sensor. In order to properly survey the Use Cases both manual and pre-programmed flights were planned and executed. The mapping parameters like the image overlap (forward & side), camera angle and flight altitude were properly adjusted according to the needs and complexity of each area. Moreover, multiple free flights were performed to acquire the necessary images for the facades of the infrastructures (Figure 15).

Figure 15: The sparse cloud that was produced and the position of the acquired images (Use Case B).

The Remote Controller is an integral part of the UAS and plays a fundamental role in the data acquisition process and the functionality of the GCS. Its primary function is to communicate with the mobile unit, send and receive data and information, while at the same time transmit the operator's commands. It is a wireless device that allows the control of the aircraft when it flies and has the following functionalities:

- Telemetry;
- Monitoring:
 - Flight information;
 - Aircraft energy level;
 - Navigation;
 - Live image;
 - Air traffic data;
 - GNSS information;
 - Temperature;
 - Other parameters;
- Planning of automatic procedures (automatic flight);
- Use of payloads and sensors;
- Use of safety measures;
- Systems configuration.

The data that the aircraft acquired (digital images, flight information, metadata, etc.) during the flights were transferred and stored to the GCS laptop computer using the remote controllers and a wireless connection. The data acquisition process using the UAS can be challenging or even impossible to achieve due to several restrictions. The weather conditions may not make it possible to plan and execute a flight, the vegetation and terrain may also be a restriction since the aircraft is not able to go near any obstacles and high trees may cover the infrastructures leading to lack of information. Other

parameters that should be taken into consideration are the flight time limitation of the UAS (approximately 30 min) and the storage limitation of all the GCS components.

Figure 16: The data during the acquisition were transferred and stored to the GCS.

1.8.3 Digital RGB High-Resolution data acquisition and processing

In order to fully document the areas and infrastructures of Use Cases A, B and C a large number of digital RGB images were taken in different ways according to the size, complexity and level of detail of each area using the DJI Zenmuse P1 full frame sensor (size 35.9×24 mm) mounted to the DJI Matrice 300 RTK in cases B and C, while the DJI M3 RTK was used for Use Case A. All the acquired images were transferred and stored to the GCS. The Table 3 presents the number and size of RGB data, which were acquired for each Use Case.

Use Case	Aerial Images (RGB)
Use Case A	
○ Braila Area	273 (2.13GB)
○ Galati Area (3 sub-areas)	11709 (120.86GB)
Use Case B	1102 (10.07GB)
Use Case C	483 (7.64GB)

Table 3: RGB Aerial Images acquired per Use Case

The data processing procedure focused on the exploitation of both the photogrammetric data and the laser scanning data to produce a complete and uniform point cloud. First the digital images were processed using the Image Based Modelling (IBM) software Agisoft Metashape v.1.8.3 following the standard workflow as in every survey process. The captured images for each Use Case were loaded, examined and evaluated for their quality. The next step was the manual detection of the pre-marked targets (GCPs) to facilitate the alignment, scaling and georeferencing of each 3D point cloud. After the successful alignment of the images, the dense point cloud was generated. Then the point clouds were evaluated and based on the point confidence, the inevitable noise was cleaned to improve the 3D mesh and Digital Elevation Models (DEM) that were produced based on the point clouds. The

resolution of the produced DEMs for Use Case A is ranging 10.7-11 cm/pixels, for Use Case B is 5.67 cm/pixels and for Use Case C is 2.78 cm/pixels (Figure 17). The resolution of the produced orthomosaics for Use Case A is 2.7 cm/pixels, for Use Case B is 2.83 cm/pixels and for Use Case C is 1.39 cm/pixels (Figure 18).

Figure 17: The produced DEMs for Use Cases A, B and C (left to right).

Figure 18: The produced orthomosaics for Use Cases A, B and C (left to right).

1.8.4 Terrestrial Laser Scanning and processing

Terrestrial laser scanning was also conducted to accurately determine the surface of the infrastructures of Use Case B to be used as reference for the routine and post-disaster monitoring along with the 3D surface which will be produced with the SfM-MVS procedure. The Leica BLK 360 Laser Scanner was used to perform the scans at the Grain Warehouse (B7) of the Freeport in Budapest (Figure 19). The scanner was remotely operated using an Apple iPad Pro dedicated tablet running the Leica Cyclone Field 360 App, which allows the user to automatically capture, register and examine scan and image data on-site, thus ensuring completeness of the data acquisition. All the data from the scanner unit were stored in the tablet and they were transferred at the GCS laptop using a wireless connection.

Figure 19: The infrastructure of Use Case B that was surveyed in detail was the Grain Warehouse (B7) in the blue box.

A total number of 17 scans (4.88 GB) were performed in Budapest to survey the Grain Warehouse (B7) and Figure 20 shows the position of the performed scans.

Figure 20: The position of the overall scans that were performed in Budapest to survey the Grain Warehouse (B7).

The data processing of the acquired point clouds started with the registration using the Cyclone Register 360 (BLK Edition) software applying the Cloud-to-Cloud method since the overlap between the scans was large enough, while the aligned scans were then georeferenced by identifying the targets and setting the coordinates of the measured GCPs. The point cloud of each area was further processed using the Geomagic Wrap 2017 to reduce inevitable scanner errors (noise) and reduce the number of points leading to a smoother, lighter and more accurate 3D point cloud and model.

1.8.5 LiDAR data acquisition and processing

The LiDAR mapping was performed using the DJI Zenmuse L1 sensor on DJI Matrice 300 RTK UAS in both Use Case B & C, while for Use Case A the same UAS was used but with the GEOSUN GS-130X sensor. Matrice 300 RTK with Zenmuse L1 sensor integrates a Livox LiDAR module, a high-accuracy inertial measurement unit, and an RGB camera. This camera has a 1-inch CMOS sensor, and the package is mounted on a three-axis stabilized gimbal. The combination of using the DJI M300 along with the L1 sensor and the Terra software for flight planning and postprocessing provides a simplified workflow for any field work. In addition, the Matrice 300 RTK coupled with GEOSUN GS-130X sensor provide an overall system that integrates a high-performance Hesai XT32 laser scanner, GNSS, and IMU positioning systems, allowing for the collection of high-resolution point cloud data and imagery with an accuracy of ± 1 cm.

Data capturing is usually carried out in an autonomous flight mode to ensure consistency and repeatability, and this was the method used in all Use Cases (see Figure 21). The first step of the data acquisition process was the area and flight planning to identify the area that needs to be surveyed and adjust the parameters concerning the overlap, speed, type of flight route, etc. Then the camera settings need to be adjusted for the LiDAR payload. The camera parameters (ISO, shutter, and EV value) need to be altered according to the operational environment.

Figure 21: The LiDAR data acquired for Use Cases A, B and C (left to right).

DJI Terra software was used to process the raw LiDAR data and generate the .las files through a streamlined workflow. First, the raw LiDAR data were imported, and a project was set up, defining the necessary settings like the coordinate system and processing parameters in each case. The software then pre-processed the data by georeferencing them, then removed the inevitable noise, and finally the point cloud alignment was performed. After generating a preliminary point cloud, DJI Terra applies filters to remove outliers and noise, resulting in a cleaner dataset. Finally, the refined point cloud was exported as a .las file, ready for further analysis in other applications.

1.8.6 Multispectral data acquisition

The multispectral data acquisition was performed using the MicaSense RedEdge-P (with luminosity sensor) on DJI Matrice 300 RTK UAS in both Use Case B & C. The MicaSense RedEdge-P sensor provides multiple options for integration – from stand-alone to fully customized integrations. Advanced integrations take advantage of flexible interfaces including ethernet, serial, and PWM/GPIO trigger, for seamless integration with any aircraft. The resolution is 1456 x 1088 (1.58 MP per multispectral band) and the pixel size is 3.45 μm . Table 4 shows the centre wavelengths and bandwidth for each band.

Band	Centre	Bandwidth
Blue	475 nm	32 nm
Green	560 nm	27 nm
Red	668 nm	16 nm
Red edge	717 nm	12 nm
Near infrared	842 nm	57 nm
Panchromatic	634.5 nm	463 nm

Table 4: Specifications of the available bands of the MicaSense RedEdge-P sensor

The MicaSense sensor includes a grey plastic box containing a QR code (used in processing software) and a large white square which is the ‘panel’ that can be used to calibrate the reflectance values of the sensor. Reflectance panels (CRP) are an important tool used to ensure the radiometric quality of datasets. The panel acts as a reference value in the calibration process, as it has a well characterised and documented reflectance profile across the spectral range captured by the sensor (Figure 22). By having a target with a known and expected spectral response, the processing workflow is able to compensate for different illumination conditions between image acquisitions. It is important to capture images that are representative of light conditions at the time of flight. Before performing the flights, the sensor was properly calibrated by capturing images of the panel both before and after the flight ensuring that the lighting conditions do not change and that there are no shadows cast on the CRP.

Figure 22: The calibration process of the MicaSense RedEdge-P sensor during the data acquisition in Use Case C.

The flight plans that were pre-programmed and imported at the GCS were loaded at the smart controller, the flights were performed and the overall areas of interest in each Use Case were covered. The Table 5 presents the number of images and size of data that were acquired for each Use Case.

Use Case	Aerial Images (Multispectral)
Use Case B	511 x 6 Bands (12.9GB)
Use Case C	1579 x 6 Bands (41.4GB)

Table 5: Multispectral aerial images acquired per Use Case

The data were transferred and stored to the GCS while the data processing was performed using the Agisoft Metashape v.1.8.3 software. The software identifies the multispectral images as a multi-camera system during import as well as the calibration images. In order to use the higher resolution panchromatic band to align the data, the Panchro Band was set as primary channel, while all the images were radiometrically calibrated. To implement the calibration the reflectance of the dataset was calibrated by locating the panels and loading the reflectance values.

Then the standard workflow of any photogrammetric processing was followed by aligning the photos, identifying common points and matching those among the images. The result of the alignment is a sparse point cloud and the computed camera locations. Then a denser point cloud (Figure 23) is produced and after that the 3D mesh and digital elevation model. Finally, the orthomosaic for each Use Case was produced and all the available products were exported.

Figure 23: The point clouds that were produced using the multispectral data for Use Case B (top) and Use Case C (bottom).

1.9 GS and GCS integration to the PLOTTO platform

The data produced by PLOTTO GCS will be integrated with Task 5.3, which focuses on multi-sensor flow and degradation assessment, and Task 5.4, which addresses multi-sensor synoptic assessment for various disaster scenarios. This integration will be achieved using the PLOTTO Middleware as data storage. More specifically the data produced by the PLOTTO GCS are stored in the Middleware SFTP server, and they are accessible through the Middleware interfaces to the rest PLOTTO components.

In the Figure 24 the flow of data to and from the PLOTTO GCS is presented.

Figure 26: UAV mission route presentation on Engage on the right and on QGIS on the left.

Once the GCS has gathered the necessary data, it forwards this information to MIDDLEWARE using Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) to ensure secure data transmission. Figure 27 presents the directories in the SFTP server that host the uploaded satellite data, as well as the UAV flight data collected.

Figure 27: Satellite data stored in the PLOT0 SFTP server in the Middleware.

In this context middleware functions as an intermediary layer that receives the data from the Multi-Satellite & UAV GCS via SFTP. Although the specific operations performed by the middleware are not detailed in the diagram, it can be inferred that the middleware further processes, stores, or routes the data as required for subsequent PLOT0 components.

2 Multi-sensor flaw and degradation assessment

Inland waterways play a significant role in citizens' everyday life, for instance, they are used for transportation and tourism purposes, among others. Simultaneously, the rivers are very complex environments which are changed drastically over time. Additionally, they are highly affected by climate change and extreme weather events, resulting in floods, drought and damages to critical infrastructures like ports, bridges etc. River monitoring techniques could provide informative products for the river management organizations, diversely. First and foremost, the prediction of an upcoming hazard due to extreme weather conditions is of high significance, to protect both the civilians and the infrastructures. Secondly, in case of an event a rapid assessment of the affected areas, during and after of it is crucial to provide sufficient information for the authorities and the upcoming operations. In this subsection, we use multimodal data i.e., Satellite and UAV imageries, 3D point cloud data etc. to enhance the resilience of inland waterways against climate change. Specifically, the satellite data are used to provide regularly updated reference maps e.g., surface water and land use land cover, which are then used to create informative, vector and raster products for the end users. Furthermore, different airborne sensors were used for the creation of 3D models of critical infrastructures in different sensing dates resulting in 4D representations of them.

2.1 Flood detection

In fact, mapping dynamic environments, like rivers, is a demanding process, which commonly incorporates the manual intervention of experts (Hossain, Gan and Baki, 2013; Li *et al.*, 2023). Specifically, water mapping is an application that has been investigated by the scientific community since decades. The optical sensing instruments carried on satellite constellations e.g., Multispectral Instrument (MSI), collects earth reflectance radiance in multiple wavelengths. Sentinel 2 constellation provides 13 bands of different spatial (10, 20 and 60 m) and spectral (approx. 440 nm – 2200 nm), resolutions. These bands are commonly used for mapping inland water areas. In this section, we incorporate state of the art inland water mapping deep learning algorithms, to create the binary inland water maps, instead of the commonly used inland water mapping indices e.g., NDWI. In fact, the created inland water maps are the products on which all the upcoming methods are applied.

2.1.1 Water Maps Creation

Often, inland water areas are extracted using spectral indices like NDWI (Gao, 1996), MNDWI and LSWI (Chandrasekar *et al.*, 2010) etc. More concretely, spectral indices perform calculations between specific bands to identify the areas of interest e.g., water, vegetated or building, or to derive informative conclusions about their characteristics. Although, NDWI was initially proposed for the estimation of vegetation liquid water using satellite images (Gao, 1996), it is commonly exploited for the extraction of surface water areas. However, there are limitations of using NDWI for inland water mapping especially using images with high cloud convergence (Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua, 2017, 2020; Luo, Tong and Hu, 2021). Additionally, applying NDWI should be followed by thresholding the image, to create the water maps, by a unique threshold value for each image and so it should be redefined in every execution. Although, NDWI has some limitations compared to the deep learning approaches, its water maps could be easily incorporated into the developed river monitoring pipeline, especially for images without clouds.

In this effort, two deep learning algorithms i.e., WatNet and DeepWaterMap (Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua, 2017, 2020; Luo, Tong and Hu, 2021) are used for inland water mapping. Figure 28 shows the water maps created using the deep learning methods. The created water maps are updated regularly i.e., whenever a new satellite image is available, and exploited as reference data for the developed approaches.

Figure 28: Visualization of water maps created using the WatNet and DeepWaterMap architectures.

2.1.2 WatNet Architecture

The WatNet (Luo, Tong and Hu, 2021) architecture is based on an encoder-decoder structure (Figure 29). In more detail, the WatNet architecture consists of two main parts, the (i) MobileNetV2 (Sandler *et al.*, 2019). al. 2018) and (ii) DeepLabV3+ (Chen *et al.*, 2018) in an encoder-decoder fashion. Specifically, the MobileNetV2 was used as the encoder part while the DeepLabV3+ as the decoder. Furthermore, the MobileNetV2 encoder was improved, by the authors of the WatNet architecture, to process multispectral satellite images instead of 3-channel images, to capture different level of features and to create fine scale prediction maps. Moreover, the Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP) (Chen *et al.*, 2018) module was included into the DeepLabV3+ part to extract multiscale features by exploiting spatial pyramids. Finally, the WatNet architecture was trained using backpropagation and Adam optimization along with the binary cross-entropy loss.

Figure 29: WatNet Architecture (Luo et. al. 2021).

2.1.3 DeepWaterMap Architecture

The DeepWaterMapV2 architecture (Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua, 2017, 2020), is based on the DeepWaterMapV1 architecture (Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua, 2017) (Figure 30). More concretely, the DeepWaterMapV1 architecture is an encoder-decoder architecture drawing inspiration from the FCN (Long, Shelhamer and Darrell, 2015) and ResNet (He *et al.*, 2016) networks. To be more specific, the encoder is defined by multiscale convolution-batch normalization and ReLU activation function along with Pooling operations. Furthermore, the decoder is defined using the same structure but incorporating upsampling and concatenation layers in addition to the convolution, batch normalization and ReLU layers. Additionally, the authors exploited two types of skip connections based on the FCNs and ResNet, respectively. Based on the DeepWaterMapV1 the authors proposed the new generation of the algorithm called DeepWaterMapV2 resulting to a more memory efficient architecture.

Figure 30: DeepWaterMap Architecture (Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua, 2017, 2020).

2.1.4 Water Maps Assessment

In general, the deep learning algorithms are evaluated using metrics like the accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and Intersection over Union (IoU), and so valuable conclusions can be drawn for the performance of the developed model. The authors of the WatNet and DeepWaterMap architectures provide different metrics for their algorithms. However, the created water maps should be evaluated separately to decide if the inference step of such algorithms was the appropriate regarding the requirements of PLOTO or a fine-tuning process is necessary. Hence, a manual annotation of the main water areas of Sentinel 2 images was conducted to assess the performance of the algorithms to the pilot sites. Figure 31 displays some of the manual annotated images for the assessment of the created water maps. In total, the manually annotated images used for the assessment of the inference step of the two algorithms were 23. Of course, the authors of the papers presented a more detailed assessment of their algorithms.

Figure 31: Sample of the manual annotated Sentinel 2 images.

Afterwards, the water maps for the same images were created by using the inference pipeline of the WatNet and DeepWaterMap algorithms. Finally, the ground truth images created manually, and those created using the deep learning algorithms were compared to calculate the accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and IoU metrics. Table 6 includes the metrics presented by the authors of the deep learning algorithms along with those calculated using the manually annotated images.

Algorithm	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Overall Acc (%)	mIoU (%)
WatNet	96.6	96.7	---	98.8	96.5
DeepWaterMap V1 & V2	88 (av. 1, 3, 5)	89 (av. 1, 3, 5)	89 (av. 1, 3, 5)	---	---
	97	90	93	---	---
WatNet (Pilot Sites)	85.9	89.2	87.4	98.2	83.5
DeepWaterMap (Pilot Sites)	89.5	92.8	91.03	98.5	85.2

Table 6: Water Maps metrics

To conclude, the performance of the algorithms satisfies the PLOT requirements and so hereafter they are used in the developed pipeline for the water maps creation step.

2.1.5 Products

In fact, the created water maps are served as regularly updated reference data for the upcoming products. The end users, which will use the developed algorithms, should be benefited by the products

and use them to extract meaningful conclusions for the monitoring area. To this end, the created water maps are used for both the creation of raster and vector products. On the one hand, the raster products are the water maps, and the riverside extraction of the monitoring area. On the other hand, the vector data are in points, lines or polygons format depending on the type of the mapping objects. To be more specific, the developed pipeline extracts the water area, of the monitored area, in shapefile (.shp) format and as polygon or line type. In the continuation we delve into the creation of such products.

2.1.6 Shoreline Extraction in Raster Format

The water map of each region could be used for the extraction of the riverside of the rivers. In fact, the rivers shoreline is the line which separates the water area from the non-water area. So, by applying, an edge detector on the created water maps we can extract the shoreline of the river in raster format. Of course, the riverside extraction product is georeferenced and thus measurements with around ± 10 m accuracy (Sentinel 2, pixel size) could be performed depending on the missing pixels. Figure 32 shows an example of the shoreline extraction as a raster product.

Figure 32: The shoreline extraction product.

2.1.7 Water Area in Vector Format

Using the created water maps, a fully automatic procedure exploiting the geopandas library was developed to transform the raster water maps into vector data resulting in the water area in polygons and lines format in a .shp file. In fact, the created product could be added into a GIS software and exploiting the attribute table to update them with many useful information. The created pipeline exports the water areas of each image in a separate file. Figure 33 depicts the vectorized water areas for each pilot case.

Figure 33: Water Areas in Vector Format Polygon and Line. Polygons WatNet (first), Polygons DeepWaterMap (second), Lines WatNet (third) and Lines DeepWaterMap (fourth).

2.2 Islet Detection and Vectorization

The river islets are commonly considered for several applications e.g., inland water navigation and transportation, river monitoring and mapping among others. However, the dynamic environment of inland waterways makes the mapping of islets a demanding task. Hence the contribution of experts exploiting GIS software and satellite images, is required. Since decades the scientific community utilize satellite images for river monitoring applications due to the temporal and rich information provided by them for any place on earth. Most of the river monitoring methods, e.g., those investigating and mapping river islets, propose a manual workflow in which they utilize satellite images time series in combination with GIS algorithms (refs) to extract the desired information. Despite the high-quality results, these methods have serious limitations, such as the small monitoring area capability, the required expertise of the users and the human resources required in every application. Finally, the available manually annotated data about river islets are limited compared to other applications like

flood mapping. In this subsection an automated approach for islets detection, and vectorization along the entire length of rivers, is described. The presented approach exploits the created water maps by the WatNet and DeepWaterMap architectures along with conventional GIS algorithms for vectorization e.g., raster vectorization, lines to polygons conversion and polygons centre point calculation. In fact, the water maps are used as input to an automated GIS workflow, which exports the: (i) multi-point, (ii) multi-polygon and (iii) multi-line, GIS layers (.gpkg) resulting to the vectorized forms of the detected islets.

First and foremost, the created water maps, which have 10 x 10 m spatial resolution, are passed into automated raster polygonization. Hereafter, each water map is accompanied with a set of vector shapes. The extracted shapes are passed into a filtering step, which filters out the outliers based on the polygons' area. If the shape is a water area, it is labelled with 255, otherwise it is labelled with 0. In fact, islets are small areas, labelled with 0, which are surrounded by areas labelled with 1. Hence, the polygons representing the islets are separated from all the rest and stored as a “.gpkg” file. Finally, the polygon shapes are transformed into line shapes and the central point of each polygon is calculated. Both the lines and the points are stored in different files (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Polygons, Lines and Points of two detected islets.

2.3 Land cover changes for Islets Categorization

Based on Land Use Land Cover (LULC) information the vectorized islets are classified into “new”, “missing” and “existing” creating an informative output for the user. To achieve that, land cover change information is used, by creating LULC change detection maps. In fact, the proposed approach uses the Copernicus scene classification product, to classify the previously vectorized islets into the “missing”, “existing” and “new” ones, providing to the user an informative output for river monitoring purposes.

First and foremost, this module uses a time series of Sentinel 2 L2A product images for the monitoring area. Then the user specifies the “base” image, which is used as reference to the normal condition of the river. Afterwards, each image in the time series is compared to the reference image to find the pixels, which changed from “water” to “land”. More concretely, the water map created for the base image and the Copernicus Scene Classification product of the image under process, are compared to produce a land cover change map, which indicates the pixels changed from “Water” to “Land” i.e., triggered pixels. Finally, the islets are categorized into “missing”, “existing” and “new” ones based on the triggered pixels inside each islet vector. In detail, if the number of triggered pixels divided by the total number of pixels inside the islet polygon, is less than a threshold the islet is classified as “existing”,

otherwise it is classified as “new”, “missing” are the islets presented in a previous image but are not presented in the new one (Figure 35). The threshold value indicates the sensitivity of the method and by default is set to 0.3.

Figure 35: Islet Categorization.

2.4 Defining Monitoring Space

The end-users may want to monitor a predefined area of the river. Thus, the developed pipeline gives the opportunity to define the monitoring area using a line vector. To be more specific, the user could digitize once the monitored area using a GIS software and then to export it as .shp file. Then, the .shp is fed into the algorithm, which produced a new inference image including only the region of interest (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Defining a new monitoring space using vector data.

2.5 Experiment under real conditions

Worldwide news media have been for days highlighting the worrying rise of the Danube's water level in December 2023. Flood alerts were issued across Hungary as the Danube water level reached its highest point since 2013. Since, the developed workflow was improved and became mature enough to be tested in near-real-time scenarios; it was applied on the ongoing event in Hungary. Figure 37

depicts two satellite images of the area of interest (Budapest, Hungary) acquired on 16th October 2023 (Fig. 37a) and 28th December 2023 (Fig. 37b), respectively.

Figure 37: Satellite images of Use Case B.

The goal of the PLOTO project is to improve the resilience of riverine urban and rural areas against the extreme weather events. Thus, the ongoing event in Budapest presents an “opportunity” for PLOTO project to assess the river monitoring modules developed so far in near-real-time scenarios to examine both their advantages and its limitations. Using the downloaded images, the PLOTO workflow resulted in many informative products (Figure 38), which can be used by experts for further examination. First and foremost, the water colour between the two images is different i.e., changed from blue to brown, indicating the water quality and the load of sediment in the river.

Figure 38: Satellite images of Use Case B.

An examination of the results shows a difference between the bank lines and the total area of the islet, significant indicators of the raise of Danube's water level. By comparing the red and green lines in Figure 36, it can be noticed that the width of the river is larger on the 28th of December than on 16th of October. In fact, the change of the bank line between the two dates is almost 100 m (Figure 37a). Additionally, the area of the islet has been significantly reduced between the two dates i.e., green polygon on 16 Oct. 2023 and red polygon on 28 Dec. 2023, which is also an indicator about the rise of Danube's water level. The developed methods could be easily used to create river monitoring alerts for extreme weather events to improve the resilience of the near river urban and rural areas. To conclude, the automated workflow developed so far, for inland water mapping and analysis, in PLOTO project gives promising results even in near-real-time scenarios, as it was expected.

2.6 Infrastructure deformations

In the PLOTO project, state-of-the-art deep learning techniques to detect flaws in construction using image data captured by UAVs were leveraged. The primary models utilized in this endeavor were YOLO v8 (Swathi and Challa, 2024) (You Only Look Once) for object detection and Meta AI's Segment Anything Model (SAM) for image segmentation.

Figure 39: YOLO v8 network architecture.

YOLO v8 (Figure 39) is an advanced object detection model renowned for its balance between speed and accuracy. YOLO models perform detection in a single forward pass, enabling real-time applications. For our project, YOLO v8 was trained on annotations derived from UAV test flights, forming the ground truth dataset. This dataset comprised images annotated with bounding boxes indicating the presence and location of construction flaws. Key features of YOLO v8 include a unified detection framework that processes the entire image at once, predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities simultaneously. It achieves high detection speeds, essential for processing large volumes of UAV-captured images, while maintaining a high level of accuracy, which is crucial for identifying even small defects in construction (‘Performance Benchmark of YOLO v5, v7 and v8’, 2023; Swathi and Challa, 2024, 2024).

To increase the granularity of our defect detection, Meta AI’s Segment Anything Model (SAM) was employed. SAM is designed to provide precise segmentation masks for objects within an image. By applying SAM to the bounding boxes generated by YOLO v8, detailed flaw segmentation masks were derived. SAM excels in producing accurate segmentation masks, allowing for detailed characterization of construction flaws. It can segment a wide variety of object types, making it suitable for diverse defect types encountered in construction, and it effectively complements object detection models like YOLO by refining their output into precise segmentations (Rafaat, 2023).

To provide geo-localized defect cataloguing, the image metadata provided by the UAV was utilized, including GPS location, altitude, and camera sensor parameters. The transformation process from pixel coordinates to GPS coordinates involved several steps. Firstly, each UAV-captured image was accompanied by metadata containing the GPS location (latitude and longitude), altitude, and camera intrinsic parameters (focal length, sensor size, etc.). From the segmentation masks generated by SAM, the pixel coordinates of detected flaws were extracted.

Using the camera parameters, a perspective transformation to convert the pixel coordinates into real-world coordinates relative to the UAV’s position was applied. This involved constructing the camera’s intrinsic matrix based on the focal length and sensor size, determining the extrinsic parameters (rotation and translation) of the camera based on UAV orientation, and applying the inverse of the

projection matrix to convert image plane coordinates (pixel coordinates) to 3D world coordinates. Finally, the 3D world coordinates were translated to GPS coordinates by factoring in the UAV's GPS location and altitude. This step ensured that the detected flaws were accurately geolocated on the construction site.

Through this comprehensive process, we were able to catalogue construction defects with precise geospatial information, significantly enhancing the utility of UAV imagery in construction monitoring and maintenance (Figure 40). By integrating YOLO v8 and SAM models with advanced geospatial transformation techniques, the PLOTO project has developed a robust framework for detecting and cataloguing construction flaws, paving the way for more efficient and effective construction management practices.

Figure 40: Asset (building) in Use Case B and defect detection using multiclass object detection model (YOLO V8).

3 Multi-sensor synoptic assessment for different disaster scenarios

3.1 Disaster scenarios

This section describes disaster scenarios for all three use cases: Use Case A (Romania pilot site), Use Case B (Budapest area) and Use Case C (Wallonia Area) (Table 7). Two main disaster categories have been identified in this task: floods and obstructions on waterways and inland infrastructure. In continuation, disaster scenarios and their repercussions on the community and economy are explored in detail, together with different sensor strategies that mitigate disaster impacts.

Use Case	Disaster Scenario	Sensor Strategy
Use Case A	Flooding event	Satellite data
Use Case A	Obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure	Satellite data, UAV data
Use Case B	Flooding event	Satellite data
Use Case B	Obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure	Satellite data, UAV data
Use Case C	Flooding event	Satellite data
Use Case C	Obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure	Satellite data, UAV data

Table 7: The disaster scenarios per Use Case

3.1.1 Flooding event

Extreme weather events, such as intense rainfall and snow melting, increase water levels in rivers and lakes, setting the stage for potential flooding (Nobre *et al.*, 2017). The situation escalates rapidly with the onset of sudden rainfalls and storm surges, which can cause water levels to rise abruptly, overwhelming the banks of rivers and leading to immediate flooding scenarios. Such events have far-reaching impacts, notably interrupting the flow of waterborne logistics and causing significant delays in the transportation of passengers and goods alike (Jonkeren and Rietveld, 2016).

Moreover, the repercussions of flooding extend well beyond these immediate disruptions. They include profound damage to residential properties, agricultural fields, and vital infrastructure (Forzieri *et al.*, 2018). The financial toll of repairing and restoring these areas can be astronomical, placing a heavy burden on communities and governments alike. Beyond the damage to human-made structures, floods also pose a significant threat to the natural environment. The powerful currents associated with flooding can erode soil, stripping away the fertile top layer and causing the dramatic collapse of riverbanks and cliffs. This erosion is not just a loss of land; it signifies the loss of agricultural potential and the disruption of natural habitats.

The aftermath of flooding is straightforwardly visible in the form of ruin and devastation, showcasing the immediate impacts of the natural disaster. On the other hand, long-term effects can only be detectable after the water recedes and by damage assessment teams (Sánchez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2019).

Today, damage assessment teams play a vital role in evaluating the extent of the impact, a process that historically has been both time-consuming and fraught with risks for those involved. Advancements in technology, particularly remote sensing techniques utilizing satellite data (Ouma, 2016) and drone imagery (Yao, Qin and Chen, 2019) have revolutionized how flood damage and its effects are assessed. These tools allow for a comprehensive evaluation of the affected areas from a safe distance, providing critical information swiftly and efficiently (Joyce *et al.*, 2009). Through remote sensing, the dynamics of flood damage can be captured in real-time, enabling quicker response and strategies without exposing assessment teams to unnecessary dangers. This technological leap enhances the effectiveness of post-disaster assessments and contributes to more proactive disaster preparedness and management efforts. Summary of flooding event in terms of its genesis, significance/hazard, dynamics, and visible and invisible indicators is presented in Table 8.

Aspect	Details	Use Case
Genesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extreme weather events (intense rainfall, snow melting, and storm surges), • Natural debris, such as fallen trees, landslides, and floating or submerged debris. 	A, B, C
Significance/Hazard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockages and obstacles in waterways, • Transportation delays, • Increased operational costs for shipping companies, • Obstruction of critical land infrastructure, • Risks for ground-based assessments teams. 	A, B, C
Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediate water damage, • Accumulation of debris in waterways and inland infrastructure, • Reduced navigability due to obstructions, • Blocked bridges, roads, and railways, • High repair costs and economic losses. 	A, B, C
Visible Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fallen trees, landslides, or debris, • Accumulation of floating debris, • Blocked waterways and infrastructure, • Grounded vessels, • Obstructed bridges, roads, and railways. 	A, B, C
Invisible Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced navigability in waterways, • Structural damage to infrastructure, • Long-term economic impact due to transportation delays and increased costs. 	A, B, C

Table 8: Summary of flooding events in terms of its genesis, significance/hazard, dynamics, and visible and invisible indicators

3.1.2 Obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure

The aftermath of flood events includes immediate water damage, and the consequential risks associated with the blockages and obstacles created by natural debris. These obstructions, such as fallen trees, landslides, and the accumulation of floating debris, pose significant threats to the effectiveness and safety of transportation via waterways (Brakenridge *et al.*, 2003). Vessels navigating through these waters are at a higher risk of colliding with unseen obstacles or becoming grounded due to the reduced navigability of the waters, sometimes obscured by the debris. This situation inevitably leads to transportation delays, which, in turn, increase operational costs for shipping companies and can lead to substantial damage to the vessels themselves, affecting the maritime industry and economy. Moreover, the impact is not limited to waterways. Once the floodwaters recede, the remnants of the disaster become a challenge on land. Debris that the waters have carried can block critical infrastructure, such as bridges, roads, and railways, impeding transportation and delivery of goods and services. Obstruction of these vital transit routes results in high repair costs for local governments and transportation departments and causes significant economic losses due to the interrupted flow of commerce and logistics (Djanibekov *et al.*, 2024).

In many cases, the extent of these blockages and the damage they cause are only fully understood upon detailed inspection by damage assessment teams, making it a reactive process. However, technological advances, particularly in remote sensing, offer a proactive approach to managing these challenges. Satellite and drone imagery provide a perspective of the affected areas, allowing for a quicker and more comprehensive assessment of the damages. These tools can identify obstructions and damage to infrastructure much faster than ground-based assessments (Ouma, 2016). Consequently, they enable quicker response times for clearing debris and repairing damaged infrastructure, potentially minimizing economic losses and operational delays. Integrating these technologies into disaster response strategies represents a significant step forward in managing the aftermath of natural disasters more effectively and efficiently, ensuring a faster return to normalcy for the affected communities and economies. Summary of obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure in terms of its genesis, significance/hazard, dynamics, and visible and invisible indicators is presented in Table 9.

Aspect	Details	Use Case
Genesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extreme weather events (intense rainfall, snow melting, and storm surges), • Natural debris, such as fallen trees, landslides, and floating or submerged debris. 	A, B, C
Significance/Hazard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockages and obstacles in waterways, • Transportation delays, • Increased operational costs for shipping companies, • Obstruction of critical land infrastructure, • Risks for ground-based assessments teams. 	A, B, C
Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediate water damage, • Accumulation of debris in waterways and inland infrastructure, • Reduced navigability due to obstructions, • Blocked bridges, roads, and railways, 	A, B, C

Aspect	Details	Use Case
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High repair costs and economic losses. 	
Visible Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fallen trees, landslides, or debris, Accumulation of floating debris, Blocked waterways and infrastructure, Grounded vessels, Obstructed bridges, roads, and railways. 	A, B, C
Invisible Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced navigability in waterways, Structural damage to infrastructure, Long-term economic impact due to transportation delays and increased costs. 	A, B, C

Table 9: Summary of obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure in terms of its genesis, significance/hazard, dynamics, and visible and invisible indicators

3.1.3 Different sensor strategies

To effectively monitor and manage flood events, a combination of satellite and drone data is employed, each offering unique advantages essential for comprehensive flood assessment and mitigation. Satellite images, particularly from sentinel satellites, provide a bird's-eye view of vast areas, making them perfect for mapping the extent of flooding across entire regions. With a revisit time of five days, these satellites can regularly supply updated data, but the interval may not be sufficient for real-time crisis management (Spoto *et al.*, 2012).

Water areas can be detected via NDWI. More concretely, NDWI is calculated as a ratio between the reflected radiation and the incoming radiation of visible green (B03) and near-infrared spectres (B8A). The resulting NDWI values are in the range of -1 and 1, where positive values represent water areas and negative values represent the absence of water as water absorbs all near-infrared light. However, in practice, during disaster events, such as floods, water detection is not enough due to the five-day acquisition frequency and high probability of clouds obstructing the view during the disaster event. This issue can be mitigated by the fact that floods leave traces of land erosion and soil deposits visible months after the disaster event. Traces of floods can be detected by computing the Bare Soil Index (BSI), which is then used to extract bare land. The shortwave infrared and the red spectral bands are used to quantify the soil mineral composition, while the blue and the near-infrared spectral bands enhance the presence of vegetation. BSI serves as a valuable tool in differentiating between bare soil, vegetation, and water. In the aftermath of a flood, regions with elevated BSI values typically indicate bare soil, while low BSI values may correspond to either vegetated areas or those submerged. By comparing BSI values before and after a flood event, it becomes possible to identify changes in land cover. Areas transitioning from low to high BSI values likely underwent vegetation loss or sediment deposition as a result of the flood. Another helpful index is the NDVI index. It is primarily used to quantify vegetation greenness and clarifies vegetation density and assessing changes in plant health. Through the comparison of NDVI values before and after a flood event, it is possible to ascertain areas, where vegetation has suffered damage or depletion because of inundation. A notable decline in NDVI values in the aftermath of a flood can highlight regions that have been inundated and adversely impacted by water. Elevated soil moisture content following a flood can be inferred from diminished NDVI values, indicating vegetation stress or submergence. Combining these three indices is sufficient

for flood event area detection, which is necessary for the damage assessment and incorporating information from the infrastructure maps (Wulder *et al.*, 2019) (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Satellite indices (Left – NDWI, middle – NDVI, right – BSI).

UAVs, on the other hand, offer highly detailed and localized coverage. They can be quickly deployed to specific areas of interest, making them invaluable for conducting in-depth site-specific assessments. This immediacy and precision in data collection are particularly critical in the aftermath of a flood, where rapid response can greatly influence the outcome of relief efforts. In operational synergy, sentinel satellites' data serve the primary role of detecting water bodies linked to flooding. This capability allows for the reliable creation of broad flood maps, pinpointing areas, where water has encroached upon the land. These maps form the basis for deploying drone operations, particularly targeting regions that are heavily impacted by the flood. The drones, equipped with advanced sensors, capture detailed imagery and LiDAR data, offering insights into structural damage, debris fields, and the overall impact on infrastructure. To maximize the utility of the data collected from both platforms, georeferencing and alignment processes are undertaken. This involves accurately mapping drone data onto the satellite-derived flood extent maps to maintain spatial consistency. By overlaying high-resolution drone imagery onto the more extensive satellite maps, a comprehensive view of the flooded area is achieved. This fusion of data allows for the generation of detailed digital elevation models (DEMs), which are instrumental in assessing changes in terrain and water levels. These DEMs, combined with both macro and micro-level imagery, enable a multi-dimensional analysis of flood impact, thus offering valuable insights into the current situation and aiding in the prediction of future flood events. By understanding changes in terrain, water flow patterns, and potential choke points, authorities can better prepare for and possibly mitigate the effects of future flooding.

The integrated use of satellite and UAV technology provides a powerful toolkit for flood management. While satellites offer wide-area coverage necessary for regional assessments, drones fill the critical need for rapid, detailed examination of specific locations. Together, they deliver a comprehensive dataset that supports effective decision-making during flood events, highlighting the importance of technological synergy in environmental monitoring and disaster response strategies.

3.2 System components

An architectural design of the system components for the detection of impending hazards and rapid post-disaster damage assessment, capable of handling multiple sensory data sources and streams, is presented in the Figure 42. The system design closely follows the JDL/DFIG (Joint Directors of Laboratories/ Data Fusion Information Group) (Blasch, 2015) methodology to effectively assess multimodal data through different levels of data fusion, as shown in the Figure 42. Each data fusion level aims to generalize and simplify the data consumed within the next level. Thus, it enables the reduction of coupling of the data products, making different assessment steps more modular by the design.

Figure 42: Architecture design based on JDL/DFIG model.

The JDL/DFIG model is a framework that categorizes the data fusion-related functions into six levels, depending on the processing stage and the type of information produced. The six levels are:

- **Level 0 – Data Assessment:** This level involves the processing of raw data from multiple sources, such as sensors, spatial databases, airborne LiDAR and satellite images, to enhance the quality, reliability, and relevance of the data. This may include tasks, such as filtering, calibration, transformation, spatio-temporal registration, segmentation, feature extraction, geometry reprojection, or data compression.
- **Level 1 – Object Assessment:** This level involves estimation of the state of individual entities or objects of interest, such as disaster events. This includes tasks such as detection, identification, classification, or tracking of the disaster events.
- **Level 2 – Situation Assessment:** This level involves the evaluation and interpretation of the state of the environment or the context, in relation to the disaster events. This includes tasks such as situation recognition, situation modelling, situation understanding, or anomaly detection. Practical example of this level is list of the affected infrastructure after disaster event.
- **Level 3 – Treat Assessment:** This level involves the assessment and prediction of the impact or consequences of the current or future situation, in relation to the goals and objectives of the user or the system. This may include tasks such as threat assessment, risk assessment, impact analysis, cost estimation, or decision support.
- **Level 4 – Process Refinement:** This level involves the optimization and adaptation of the data fusion process, and the resources involved, such as sensors, networks, or algorithms. This may include tasks, such as sensor management, network management, task allocation, feedback control, or in case of T5.4, development of the automated tool for outputting the list of damaged infrastructure in form of spatial maps ready for visualization within existing GIS applications or frameworks (ArcGIS, QGIS, OpenLayers, MapBox).
- **Level 5 – User Refinement:** This level involves the interaction and collaboration between the data fusion system and the human user, to improve the usability, understandability, and trustworthiness of the data fusion results. This may include tasks such as data visualization, data explanation, user feedback, or user modelling.
- **Level 6 – Mission Refinement:** This level involves the alignment and coordination of the data fusion system and the human user with the overall mission or purpose of the system. This may include tasks, such as mission planning, mission execution, mission evaluation, or mission adaptation.

The system for multi-sensor synoptic assessment for different disaster scenarios focuses on the first three levels, i.e., Level 0 – Data Assessment, Level 1 – Object Assessment, and Level 2 – Situation Assessment, for detecting flooded areas and identification of obstructed or damaged infrastructure. In step Level 0 – Data Assessment data provided from GSC is pre-processed, i.e., data is cleaned, satellite data is geospatially, and temporal aligned with UAV data, and features are extracted (e.g., satellite indices). Infrastructure maps, in our case OpenStreetMaps, are Level 1 – Object Assessment data fusion products and can be modified and supplemented with other data from national geodetic survey companies in order to add the newest features of infrastructure. If some of the data is not available, geometry can be manually digitized using existing GIS software, such as ArcGIS or QGIS.

Level 2 – Situation Assessment focuses on utilizing pre-processed data from UAVs and satellites to analyse and evaluate the current state of flood-affected areas and infrastructure. We determine the area covered by floodwaters, monitor changes over time, and identify and quantify damage to buildings, roads, bridges, and other critical infrastructure. In continuation, the whole pipeline and details, together with visual representation, from data processing to damage assessment, are presented.

3.2.1 Data preparation

Satellite data can be obtained from GCS in the form of well-established and defined indices directly from Sentinel Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem. For that, a data acquisition module is implemented that enables access to external data, such as GSC, Sentinel 2 imagery, OpenStreetMap, and other sensors. Regarding direct access to Sentinel-2, OGC services are implemented that accept spatial bounds and time frame as input arguments and return results as an image. The following bands are identified as necessary ones for the damage assessment tool developed during this task:

- B02 (Blue, Central Wavelength = 490 nm),
- B03 (Green, Central Wavelength = 560 nm),
- B04 (Red, Central Wavelength = 665 nm),
- B8A (Narrow near infrared, Central Wavelength = 865 nm),
- B11 (Shortwave infrared, Central Wavelength = 1610 nm), and
- CLDPRB (Cloud probability mask).

Indices calculated from the abovementioned bands that are used during this task are NDWI, BSI, and NDVI. UAV data is also obtained from GCS. A LiDAR survey of the area with a UAV captures the state of the situation in detail. This information is further processed to extract meaningful information into multiple data products. These products are:

- Digital Terrain Model: This consists of ground points with all surface objects removed from the final product. This product is necessary for point cloud object classification.
- Digital Surface Model: This includes heights of all surface objects.
- Surface Object Classification: which semantically maps points into the object groups, such as ground, vegetation, buildings, etcetera.
- Normal map: This map contains slopes of the surfaces.

Infrastructure geometry for the event was obtained from Geofabrik, which packages OpenStreetMap data using a standard GIS format. OpenStreetMap data contains buildings, roads, bridges, waterways, and other digitized information for the globe. It should also be noted that infrastructure maps are already level 1 data fusion products and can be easily swapped out with other data from national geodetic survey companies. In extreme cases, where data is not available, geometry can be manually digitized using existing GIS software, such as ArcGIS or QGIS.

3.2.2 Data processing

GeoPackage (OGC) file readers and writers were developed to operate on spatial data. The data structure was designed to support the representation of spatial features in a list of 3D vertices with topology information and data attributes that describe spatial objects. Each object is represented as multipoint, polyline, or polygon geometry, allowing the application of specific geometry operations, such as:

- Area calculation: This operation facilitates the computation of the surface area occupied by spatial objects, providing invaluable insights into their spatial dimensions.
- Geometry buffering: A technique used to create buffer zones around spatial objects. This is particularly useful in spatial analysis, where delineating areas of influence around objects is necessary.
- Union: This operation combines two or more spatial objects into a single unified object, thereby facilitating the synthesis of spatial information.
- Difference: Employed to identify the spatial difference between objects, this operation helps in distinguishing unique characteristics of spatial entities.
- Intersection between different spatial objects: A critical operation that identifies the common spatial area between overlapping objects, enabling intricate spatial relationship analysis.

Geometry search methods were implemented using the R-tree algorithm, which allows for the fast identification of nearby or intersecting objects. Furthermore, an integration with a generic IoT data model is implemented that enables the representation of stationary or moving IoT devices, their sensors, and data streams with observed values in a structured manner. Implemented methods for data enrichment integrate spatial and IoT or UAV data for further analysis and processing. The method is implemented that fuse this data via spatial intersection between different objects and by applying a stream from UAV sensors to the intersected geographic objects. A raster vectorization algorithm is also implemented that extracts geometry objects from this input, increasing resolution and providing better quality of final data representation. This further enhances extracted objects with additional attribute information from sensor data. Applying geometry operations on former data enables the detection of changes between different time points to generate risk assessment maps.

3.3 Damage assessment tool

The damage assessment tool, presented in the continuation, is currently deployed [here](#). It is additionally dockerized along with its libraries, dependencies, and configuration. This consumes around 13 GB of disk space to download all the layers necessary to build the DLL. Produced container images consume around 4 GB of storage. Furthermore, to facilitate the operation and integration of this tool within continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines, Jenkins integration has been prepared. A specialized pipeline was established on an external platform, denoted here as <https://jenkins.ploto.rid-intrasoft.eu/>, to automate the processes of building, testing, and deploying the application within diverse operational environments. To complement these integrations, scripts (Figure 43) to pull the docker image from the [harbor registry](#) were created and executed on sample data provided within the image.

```

1 pipeline {
2   agent {
3     node {
4       label 'dev01-PLOT0'
5     }
6   }
7
8   environment {
9     DOCKER_REG = "harbor.ploto.rid-intrasoft.eu"
10    DOCKER_REPO = "dymon"
11  }
12
13  stages {
14    stage('Test') {
15      steps {
16        withCredentials([[${class: 'UsernamePasswordMultiBinding', credentialsId:
17          'harbor-jenkins-creds', usernameVariable: 'USERNAME', passwordVariable: 'PASSWORD'}]]) {
18          sh 'docker login ${DOCKER_REG} -u ${USERNAME} -p ${PASSWORD}'
19          sh 'docker run "${DOCKER_REG}/${DOCKER_REPO}/t5.4-disasterevents
20            simple-flood-damage-assessment --inputimage "C:/SampleData/Freeport_NDWI.tif"
21            --inputbuildings "C:/SampleData/Freeport_Buildings.gpkg" --inputroads "C:/SampleData/
22            Freeport_Roads.gpkg" --inputrailroads "C:/SampleData/Freeport_Railways.gpkg"
23            --outputaffectedbuildings "C:/FloodedBuildings.json" --outputaffectedroads "C:/
24            FloodedRoads.json" --outputaffectedrailroads "C:/FloodedRailroads.json"
25            --outputdamageareas "C:/FloodedAreas.json" --outputwaterareas "C:/DetectedWater.json"'
26        }
27      }
28    }
29  }
30 }

```

Figure 43: Script sample that was used to pull the docker image from the harbor registry.

Figure 44: Status page of the tool at <https://jenkins.ploto.rid-intrasoft.eu/>.

Pilot site agnostic test of the deployed damaged infrastructure assessment tool performed on the sample data over HTTPS has been created and is deployed [here](#) (Figure 44). If RPC service with provided sample data executes and returns 200 OK with the JSON response, then service works.

In the continuation, an example of abnormal water coverage and infrastructure damage for the Budapest area in the end of December 2023 is presented. Based on the Sentinel 2 data, the system extracted water areas based on NDWI, while both already explained indices (BSI and NDVI) can be also used by the system as presented in continuation.

3.3.1 Abnormal water coverage and affected infrastructure

During an abnormal water coverage, such as flood event, water absorbs and scatters light differently than vegetation. This results in decreased NDWI values in flooded areas due to reduced reflectance in the near-infrared band caused by water. Combining NDWI, NDVI and BSI indices is therefore sufficient

for flood event area detection, which is necessary for the damage assessment and incorporating information from the infrastructure maps. In order to assess the damaged infrastructure, disaster event areas must first be detected. This is done by combining indices NDWI, NDVI and BSI with SWIR band, and by defining simple ruleset to exclude water and vegetation from detected area which outputs. Additional bands can be also considered here as they can be helpful in order to assess abnormal water coverage effects on the surrounding, as shown in Figure 45, Figure 46, and Figure 47.

Figure 45: An example of B08 (the near infrared band), useful for mapping shorelines and biomass content and at detecting vegetation.

Figure 46: An example of B03 that gives excellent contrast between clear and muddy water, while penetrating clear water fairly well and highlights a vegetation.

Figure 47: Flooding disaster event visible from Sentinel 2 images for Budapest freeport on 28.12.2023.

The next step is to extract the polygon bounds of the detected area for further situation assessment and analysis. Here, a threshold to the NDWI was applied to create a binary mask indicating water bodies (e.g., indicating $NDWI > 0$ corresponds to water). The actual geometry of the water area is then obtained from a raster using a marching squares algorithm that can extract the contours from the binary water mask. There are two benefits to operating on the actual geometry instead of rasters. First, the size is significantly reduced as connected disaster area pixels are grouped into a single polygon object. The second benefit is that arbitrary attributes can be set to the object with additional information required for further data fusion levels. These attributes also include the original pixel value within the detected group. Geometry of the water area is presented in the Figure 48.

Figure 48: Extracted polygon bound from the raster flood map.

Once the water area is identified and geometry extracted, the next step is to identify the infrastructure affected by the flooding. Here we intersect geometry of the water area with geometry of buildings,

roads and railways. Figure 49 shows an example of a new geometry layer that represents affected buildings (red) and roads/railways (black) affected by the water. The result of this step is a new geometry layer containing segments that require real world investigation.

Figure 49: Red denotes buildings affected during the floods, while black lines represents affected roads/railways.

For example, service for detecting buildings affected during the December 2023 floods for Use Case B can be accessed at this [link](#), while Table 10 summarises the input parameters of the system.

Type	Description	Name
Tiff	Input image containing water values (e.g. NDWI). This can be either mask or floating-point image, which is then thresholded via InputWaterThreshold parameter.	InputImage
ShapeLayer	Spatial layer that contains polygon geometry of buildings.	InputBuildings
ShapeLayer	Spatial layer that contains polygon geometry of roads.	InputRoads
ShapeLayer	Spatial layer that contains polygon geometry of railroads.	InputRailroads
Double	Buffer radius around line or point geometry types. This is used when intersecting with flood areas.	InputBufferUnit
Double	Water threshold value. Everything above this value is considered water.	InputWaterThreshold

Table 10: The input parameters of the system

3.3.2 Obstructions on infrastructure with UAV data

In the context of Use Case B, which focuses on the Budapest Area, a strategic approach was employed to detect obstructed infrastructure. This was achieved by leveraging LiDAR data, which is noted for its precision in capturing detailed spatial information. LiDAR data proved instrumental in identifying infrastructure aspects that were not immediately visible or had been obstructed, thus offering a deeper insight into the actual state of the area's infrastructure landscape. Existing infrastructure data

from OpenStreetMap (OSM) was incorporated into the workflow to simplify the process and enhance efficiency. Integration of OSM data played a crucial role in Use Case B by eliminating the need for the lengthy classification step typically required when working with raw LiDAR data. This is because OSM readily provides a comprehensive 2D mapping of locations and boundaries of various structures within the area of interest. The OSM can be additionally enriched by incorporating height information extracted from the LiDAR data, thus transitioning from a simple 2D representation to a more complex and informative model. This not only saves time but also enhances the accuracy and utility of the infrastructure data being analysed. Figure 50 visually depicts how extracting vertical dimensions from the LiDAR data can augment the existing OSM maps, offering a better understanding of the Budapest Area's infrastructure, from its current state to potential areas of concern that might be obstructed or otherwise not accounted for in traditional 2D maps.

Figure 50: Building height extraction from underlying LiDAR data. The extracted attributes for the selected building (light blue) are displayed on the right side. The maximum height of the building is 121 m.

Figure 51 shows the system's combination of different kinds of spatial data (Sentinel-2, infrastructure maps, LiDAR). This data is spatially and temporally aligned in the first step.

Figure 51: Spatial map of Budapest Freeport displaying railway infrastructure (orange lines), buildings (yellow), LiDAR UAV survey data of the Freeport and NDWI from Sentinel-2.

Anomaly detection on the existing infrastructure using LiDAR data is usually performed by utilizing a wide array of tools and algorithms that consist of mathematical morphology, point interpolation, surface extraction and linking, fast neighbouring point search methods from the underlying LiDAR, and geometry buffering. The first step towards point cloud analysis is to construct surfaces from point cloud data by fitting a mathematical definition of a plane to a subset of points within a processing window using a least squares method.

The resulting parameters define the best-fit plane for the given subset of points. The next step is to combine planes with similar normals together. For that, the normal vector for each fitted plane is calculated, followed by a grouping of a plane with similar normal vectors using a clustering algorithm (e.g., k-means). Each cluster represents a set of planes with similar orientations. The partial result of this method can be seen in the Figure 52 in the form of a normal map. This visual representation helps understanding the orientation and distribution of surfaces within the point cloud.

Figure 52: The output of the locally fitted surfaces algorithm is in the form of a normal map. Marked segments represent trees. The red rectangle shows the location of the tree that obstructs the railway (the rectangles define the areas to focus on).

Since the railroads are primarily composed of flat surfaces and obstacles are almost always composed of planes with normals pointing in different directions, root mean square error (RMSE) between the plane and its points is calculated. This step produces an image, where each pixel contains the RMSE value. This information is further used to detect areas that contain sudden elevation changes from the expected surface, such as trees, debris, or building walls. Visualization of the surface errors is shown in the Figure 53, and second image displaying the LiDAR cross-section of the railway with a tree obstructing the path.

Figure 53: Output of the locally fitted surfaces algorithm is in the form of point-to-surface errors. Points on flat surfaces such as roads and building rooftops do not contribute to the accumulated error value, while points far from the fitted surface contribute.

The final step includes extracting the geometry segments obstructing the railway. This step is performed by a combination of different geospatial tools, which include:

- Performing geometry buffering operation on the railway with 1 m in each direction. This step converts line geometry into polygon geometry.
- Setting a threshold of the surface errors high enough to filter out small elevation changes and extract geometry bounds.
- Intersecting geometry of the previous two steps. The result of this step is a new geometry layer, containing segments that require real-world investigation.

Figure 54: Detected obstacles on the railway that require further investigation. These obstacles are primarily due to nearby vegetation, which might require trimming from the local vegetation management service.

In developing content for Use Case C, the damage assessment tool mirrored what we had previously done for Use Case B, focusing on leveraging LiDAR technology to assess environmental changes.

Regarding the Use Case C, as demonstrated in Figure 55, the integration of LiDAR data with Sentinel-2 imagery presents a comprehensive approach to environmental monitoring and resource management. This fusion technique allows for a detailed and accurate classification of various natural features. Specifically, in Figure 56, we highlight the capability of the system to delineate water bodies by utilizing indices derived from Sentinel-2. At the same time, as shown in Figure 57, the system illustrates capacity to identify vegetation, showing the practical applications of this integrated data approach in disaster management scenarios. By identifying trees at risk of falling and becoming debris during flood conditions, as shown in Figure 58, pre-emptive measures can be taken to mitigate potential damages. This proactive approach can significantly aid in the preparedness and response phases of disaster management.

Additionally, the extraction of the Canopy Height Model (CHM) from LiDAR data opens new avenues for ecological and conservation studies (Figure 59). The detailed 3D model generated provides invaluable insights into the structure and distribution of vegetation cover, enabling targeted conservation efforts and enhancing our understanding of ecosystem dynamics during the disaster.

Figure 55: Captured LiDAR fused with Sentinel-2 imagery on Use Case C.

Figure 56: Classified water are the same data for Use Case C.

Figure 57: Classified vegetation on the same data for Use Case C.

Figure 58: Trees that poses potential danger becoming debris after the floods.

However, a significant limitation emerged, namely that the LiDAR data we currently possess doesn't capture post-hazard events. This gap in data collection means we're unable to directly observe the impact of calamities, such as the damage or obstructions caused by them.

For instance, under normal circumstances, LiDAR data could potentially offer insights into the aftermath of flood events, showing how the landscape, particularly forested areas near significant landmarks like the Albert Canal, is affected. This could include detailing the extent of flooding in these regions and identifying how many trees were submerged during and after the floodwaters receded. Such detailed, time-specific data allows for a comprehensive understanding of natural disasters' direct impacts on forested areas.

To circumvent the limitations of our current dataset, there's a potential solution that involves comparing two sets of LiDAR data taken at different times – one before the flood and another after. This comparative analysis could reveal changes in the landscape, particularly in how floodwaters interact with vegetation. By examining the differences between these two datasets, we could potentially quantify the effects of flooding, such as determining the number of trees dislodged by the water, which then contributes to the formation of new debris.

This method hinges on the availability of LiDAR data that precisely captures the before and after states of a flood event, underscoring the importance of timely and specific data collection in environmental monitoring and disaster assessment.

Figure 59: Canopy height model (CHM) generated from LiDAR.

3.4 Hazard alerts

Monitoring will operate dynamically and function in real-time. This means that, for instance, it will systematically review all available data for the use cases daily and proceed to create updated maps based on the latest information. The produced information is made available in universally recognized spatial data formats, including OGC GeoPackage and GeoJSON, with GeoJSON being the preferred format by default. This preference for GeoJSON originates from its compatibility with numerous web-mapping frameworks, including, but not limited to, OpenLayers, Leaflet, and MapBox, supporting numerous geographic projection systems. Metadata of the output from the system is available [here](#), while details are presented in the Table 11.

Type	Description	Name	Name
ShapeLayer	Affected buildings	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/romania/latest/buildings	A
ShapeLayer	Affected road infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/romania/latest/roads	A
ShapeLayer	Affected railway infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/romania/latest/railways	A

Type	Description	Name	Name
ShapeLayer	Detected flood damage areas	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/romania/latest/floods	A
ShapeLayer	Detected water from the input imagery	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/romania/latest/detectedwater	A
ShapeLayer	Affected buildings	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/budapest/latest/buildings	B
ShapeLayer	Affected road infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/budapest/latest/roads	B
ShapeLayer	Affected railway infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/budapest/latest/railways	B
ShapeLayer	Detected flood damage areas	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/budapest/latest/floods	B
ShapeLayer	Detected water from the input imagery	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/budapest/latest/detectedwater	B
ShapeLayer	Affected buildings	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/wallonia/latest/buildings	C
ShapeLayer	Affected road infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/wallonia/latest/roads	C
ShapeLayer	Affected railway infrastructure	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/wallonia/latest/railways	C
ShapeLayer	Detected flood damage areas	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-	C

Type	Description	Name	Name
		9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/wallonia/latest/floods	
ShapeLayer	Detected water from the input imagery	https://fusion.gemma.feri.um.si/gf-test/api/ws/e66d37d8-838a-40b5-ab4d-9b49b32efa83/services/processing/sites/wallonia/latest/detectedwater	C

Table 11: Details of the output from the system

4 Conclusions

WP5 and D5.1, in particular, outline a comprehensive strategy for the assessment and monitoring of IWW corridors and their adjacent disaster-affected regions. This approach utilizes multi-source remote sensing, satellite, and UAS data to enhance the effectiveness of the process. The development of the RS-MMS and its integration with the GCS constitutes a substantial advancement in data-driven decision-making for disaster preparedness, risk mitigation, and post-event recovery. The deliverable identifies several key innovations. The utilisation of multi-sensor data from satellites, UASs, and ground-based systems and sensors ensures a comprehensive and integrated view of inland waterways.

Advanced data processing techniques, including photogrammetric analysis, machine learning, and deep learning approaches, have been employed to produce high-resolution digital elevation models, three-dimensional representations (point clouds and meshes), 2D maps and orthomosaics. The multi-sensor synoptic assessment provides a robust methodology for monitoring various disaster scenarios, such as floods and obstructions in waterways like islets. This enables the rapid detection of infrastructure damage and environmental changes. Furthermore, the Damage Assessment Tool utilises multi-source data to identify abnormal water coverage and detect affected infrastructure, which is crucial for the implementation of timely response and maintenance efforts.

The PLOT platform's capacity to support real-time data acquisition, analysis, and integration will facilitate a more proactive approach to IWW management. The methodologies and tools outlined in this deliverable offer a valuable foundation that can significantly enhance predictive hazard modelling and support the advancement of automated risk assessment. The creation of a unified data repository, coupled with the implementation of a seamless data exchange through the PLOT Middleware, guarantees that partners and relevant stakeholders have access to timely, accurate, and actionable insights.

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